

Challenges and Barriers in Implementing Community Health Education Faced by BSN Students at the College of Nursing, Sir C.J Institute of Psychiatry, Hyderabad

**Zafarullah Junejo^{1*}, Mushtaque Ali Talpur^{2*},
Irfan Ali Chandio³, Farzana Soomro⁴, Yaswant Rai⁵**

^{1,2,3,4}Peoples Nursing School, Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro, Sindh-Pakistan.

⁵Assistant Professor, Bhitai College of Nursing & Allied Health Sciences, Mirpukhas, Sindh-Pakistan.

junejozafar856@gmail.com*, atalpur78@gmail.com*

*Corresponding Authors: Zafarullah Junejo, Mushtaque Ali Talpur.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15105114

ABSTRACT

Health education is essential for empowering individuals to enhance their health knowledge and make health-related decisions. The purpose of this research was to assess the challenges and barriers faced by BSN students in implementing community health education. The descriptive non-experimental design was the research methodology employed in this study. The study was done with a sample of 106 BSN students from the College of Nursing at Sir C.J. Institute of Psychiatry, Hyderabad. A structured questionnaire was utilized to identify the challenges and barriers related to health education. Descriptive statistics were used in IBM SPSS version 23 to analyze the data as frequencies and percentages. Major challenges included managing diverse client groups, preparing appropriate audiovisual aids, addressing clients' time limitations, finding suitable venues for sessions, and balancing additional clinical assignments. Significant barriers were identified, such as difficulties in translating medical terminology into the local language, noise and distractions in the environment, challenges in controlling external factors, and insufficient time to effectively evaluate the client's knowledge. The study concluded that BSN students encounter various challenges and barriers in delivering health education, relating to students, teaching materials, audiovisual aids, clients, environmental factors, and evaluation processes. Identifying these challenges is essential for developing strategies to overcome them, ultimately facilitating more effective health education in community settings.

KEYWORDS: Nursing Students, Health Education, Community Health Nursing, Challenges, and Barriers.

Cite as: Zafarullah Junejo, Mushtaque Ali Talpur (2024). Challenges and Barriers in Implementing Community Health Education Faced by BSN Students at the College of Nursing, Sir C.J Institute of Psychiatry, Hyderabad. *Mader e Milat International Journal of Nursing and Allied Sciences*, 2(4), 1–14. **10.5281/zenodo.15105114**

INTRODUCTION

Communicating information about health and nurturing the essential strengths, abilities, and self-confidence regarding personal health promotion activities as well as the persuasion needed to prompt healthy behaviors is defined as health education (Khamaiseh & Altarawneh, 2023). Health education is the intentional process of designing educational experiences that involve communication with the aim of promoting health literacy. This includes gathering knowledge as well as establishing personal and communal health life skills (Ravindra & Borude, 2023). In every society, a person has a right to be informed about their health, and health care providers have a professional responsibility to impart that knowledge (Hamidzadeh et al., 2020; Hwang & Oh, 2020). To enhance health in developing nations, health education includes a range of activities designed to raise public awareness and attitudes. In addition to imparting basic health knowledge and preventive skills, it fosters concepts that help individuals with unhealthy lifestyles alter their habits. This type of training impacts not only the students receiving the instruction directly but also subsequent generations (WHO, 2012) (Aron et al., 2023). An important component of health promotion is this issue that refers to the maintenance, repair, and change of health education for people's health. Therefore, it deals with active skills that help the person to make rational decisions about his or her health and the values connected with health and illness (Benes & Alperin, 2022).

The steps of the health education process parallel the nursing process and are divided into five categories: The first is to evaluate the clients' knowledge, knowledge gaps, learning skills or preferences, understanding, perception, interest and willingness to listen; The second is to identify the assets, limitations and learning requirements of the clients; The third is to map the educational plan and goals and choose the appropriate approaches to use; the fourth is to translate the plan into action and deliver the education; The last is to assess the educational process (Sharma, 2021; Wang et al., 2020). Nursing Students receive theoretical courses in health education and communication skills to help them apply these concepts appropriately. They are required to apply the concepts of health education while responding to clients and families. However, they encounter many challenges and constraints that occur before, during, and after teaching that affect health education whenever they address clients within teaching settings (Reid et al., 2021). Moreover, several factors hinder nursing students from employing health education compassionately, including their perceptions of the content, their responsibilities as health educators, lack of time, inadequate resources, unclear objectives, and criteria, insufficient expertise, physical and clinical environment constraints, unexpected situations and patients' unwillingness to engage in teaching interactions (Ferreira et al., 2022).

The community healthcare setting aims to provide healthcare to individuals who are not able to learn typical places like workplaces, schools, hospitals, or homes. Each environment offers opportunities to connect with individuals through the existing social networks. Nursing students perceive community health care setting as most important clinical learning environment (CLE). Students studying community nursing undergo 15 weeks of practice that includes home visits and primary care clinics in both rural and urban areas. Throughout their practical practice in community health nursing, nursing students should impart helpful health education; however, they encounter many challenges (Betancurth-Loaiza et al., 2024; Gonella et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the evidence suggests that nursing students are not engaged in patient health education, highlighting the need for analysis as a component of the evaluation of the nursing program to find out the hindrances causing this disengagement. Previous research indicates that nurses' performance in patient education is often unsatisfactory (Mohammed et al., 2019). Thus, this research aims to explore whether BSN students at the Sir C.J. Institute of Psychiatry in Hyderabad perceive challenges and barriers that impact their ability to implement health education before, during, and after the process.

Research Objectives:

- To identify the challenges faced by BSN students while implementing health education in community settings.
- To identify the barriers faced by BSN students while implementing health education in community settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An essential component of nursing practice is health education, which aims to enable people and communities to become more health literate and make informed choices regarding their health (Pueyo-Garrigues et al., 2022). Healthcare education is a purposeful act aimed at creating the ability to operationalize health information. This educational approach not only gives out information but also shapes a person's and community's health literacy skills (Rudd et al., 2023). In most societies, freedom to obtain health information is a basic human right although healthcare professionals have an ethical duty to educate clients on their state of health (Komalasari, 2024).

Importance of Health Education in Developing Countries:

Health education in developing countries covers several activities that seek to raise community awareness and encourage people to adopt necessary changes that improve their health status (Koelen & Van den Ban, 2023). According to World Health Organization (2012) enhanced conducive health education creates positive changes to health and sustainable behavioral alteration throughout generations (Rudnicka et al., 2020). Research has underscored that health education enables one to develop dynamic competencies for reasonable decisions, health-related values, and the related values of health and illness (Badulla et al., 2023).

The Health Education Process:

The health education process closely mirrors the nursing process and can be broken down into five key steps: identification of learning prerequisites, identification of learning disparities, formulation of learning plans, execution of these plans, and appraisal of learning effectiveness.

The benefits of successful health education are not only achieved in patients but also for the nursing students themselves who acquire theoretical knowledge as well as practical experience in delivering health education and related interpersonal skills (Ravindra & Borude, 2023).

Challenges Faced by Nursing Students:

Nonetheless, nursing students experience several challenges and barriers in the course of translating health education protocols. These difficulties may occur at several levels of the teaching process and may result in the possible omission of health education in clinical practice (DeMarco & Healey-Walsh, 2023). Challenges like time constraints, resource unavailability, unclear objectives, inadequate knowledge and skills, and limitations of the environment as important barriers that prevent the delivery of effective health education by the nursing students (Khamaiseh & Altarawneh, 2023).

Health Care Facilities in the Community as Educational Environments:

In particular, community healthcare facilities are needed to give health education to clients who might not be able to get to conventional healthcare facilities. Hence, it insists on the value of community health nursing clinical engagements in which nursing learners undertake shared learning through home visitations and primary care clinics. Nevertheless, as noted, students can engage in relevant and valuable education sessions, but they can encounter enormous problems in providing high-quality health teaching during these experiences (Ravindra & Borude, 2023).

Disengagement in Health Education:

Previous studies show that the majority of nursing students seem to lack the confidence and practical experience needed to effectively assume the role of nursing educators (Iduye et al., 2021). This disengagement has highlighted the need to expand the understanding of the challenges and barriers that BSN students encounter especially in community-based environments (Mohammed et al., 2019; Stock, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: A Quantitative approach.

Study Design: The study was conducted using a descriptive, non-experimental method of research.

Setting of the Research Study: College of Nursing, Sir C.J. Institute of Psychiatry, Hyderabad, a prominent institution offering a BSN program in Hyderabad, Sindh.

Study Population: BSN students from the above-mentioned institute in Hyderabad who are enrolled in Community Health Nursing courses and have taken part in community visits were included in the population.

Sample Size: 106 BSN students from the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th years were chosen using Raosoft online software apart from the first year BSN.

Sampling: Non-Probability Purposive Sampling approach.

Research Tool: Structured questionnaire which includes:

Section I: Collects Data on Demographics

Section II: Using a 3-point Likert scale, health education challenges are rated as disagree, neutral, and agree.

Section III: Uses a 3-point Likert scale with the options to "agree," "neutral," and "disagree" for assessing health education barriers.

- **Part A:** Explains the challenges before the process of health education being implemented.
- **Part B:** Customizes challenges encountered during the process of health education.
- **Part C:** Challenges faced after the health education process.

Section IV: BARRIERS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION STAGE OF HEALTH EDUCATION

- **Part A: BARRIERS RELATED TO STUDENTS.**

- **Part B: BARRIERS RELATED TO CLIENTS.**
- **Part C: BARRIERS RELATED TO ENVIRONMENT.**

Section V: BARRIERS IN THE TERMINAL STAGE OF HEALTH EDUCATION

- **Part A: BARRIERS RELATED TO EVALUATION**

Data Collection Process: The principal of the College of Nursing at the Sir C.J. Institute of Psychiatry in Hyderabad granted permission in order to do the research. The participants were asked to participate after becoming aware of the study's objectives. Those who consented to participate gave both verbal and written consent.

Data Analysis: For data analysis, IBM SPSS version 23 was utilized, and descriptive statistics were employed to provide a frequency and percentage description of the research population.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

SECTION-I

Table 1: Demographic Analysis

n=106

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage %
AGE (YEARS)		
20-22	69	65.1%
23-25	31	29.2%
26-28	4	3.8%
28-30	1	0.9%
Above 25	1	0.9%
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	91	85.8%
Married	14	13.2%
Widower	0	0.0%
Divorced	1	0.94%
YEAR OF STUDY		
2 nd Year	40	37.7%
3 rd Year	41	38.7%
Final Year	25	23.6%
PLACE OF RESIDENCE		
Day Scholar	54	50.9%
Hostler	52	49.1%

The demographic information of the research population is presented in Table 1: 65.1% are aged 20-22 and 29.2% are in the 23-25 age range. Other small groups include 3.8% between the age of 26-28 and 0.9% above the age of 28 years. As per marital status, 85.8% are single, 13.2% are married and 0.94% is divorced. In terms of study year, 38.7% of respondent indicates 3rd year, 37.7% 2nd year, and 23.6% in 1st year. The place of residence is nearly balanced with 50.9% of the recipients as day scholars and 49.1% as hostlers.

SECTION 2: ANALYSIS OF HEALTH EDUCATION CHALLENGES

Table 2: Challenges of Health Education among BSN Students

n=106

S. No	Challenges Faced By Students	Disagree		Neutral		Agree	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
1.	Language barriers make it challenging to assess clients' learning needs.	7	6.6%	11	10.4%	88	83%
2.	Unable to prioritize the problems of clients based on their needs.	33	31.1%	19	17.9%	54	50.9%
3.	Managing a large group of clients of different ages may be challenging	10	9.4%	15	14.2%	81	76.4%
4.	Challenges with delivering effective health education on sensitive topics	12	11.3%	26	24.5%	68	64.2%
5.	Finding it difficult to use modern technology and preparing proper audiovisual (AV) aids	34	32.1%	23	21.7%	49	46.2%
6.	Having difficulty in engaging clients to give attention to health-related topics	19	17.9%	30	28.3%	57	53.8%
7.	Clients' limitations on time	21	19.8%	27	25.5%	58	54.7%
8.	Educating individuals who are already knowledgeable about the topic is difficult	44	41.5%	24	22.6%	38	35.8%
9.	All Challenges in choosing an appropriate location for health education	26	24.5%	24	22.6%	56	52.8%
10.	Unable to get feedback from clients on health information	37	34.9%	19	17.9%	50	47.2%
11.	Feeling overwhelmed by other clinical responsibilities while implementing community health education into practice	28	26.4%	25	23.6%	53	50%

Challenges in providing health education are listed in Table 2: When evaluating the learning needs of their clients, 83.0% emphasize language barriers, 76.4% indicate it's hard to manage different age groups, and 64.2% find it hard to handle sensitive topics. 53.8% of respondents find it difficult to retain their attention, and 41.5% find it tough to instruct informed clients. Furthermore, 50.0% are overwhelmed by additional clinical responsibilities, and 54.7% deal with clients' constraints on time.

SECTION -3 ANALYSES OF BARRIERS TO HEALTH EDUCATION PROCESS

Table: 3 Barriers in the Health Education preparation stage

n=106

A. Barriers Related To Students	Disagree		Neutral		Agree	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
1. Unable to accurately assess the clients' learning needs	28	26.4%	18	17%	60	56.6%

2. Unable to prioritise problems with clients based on what they need.	31	29.2%	27	25.5%	48	45.3%
3. Not able to develop health education objectives based on assessment of needs.	41	38.7%	22	20.8%	43	40.6%
4. Unable of managing a large number of clients	20	18.9%	21	19.8%	65	61.3%
5. Unable to choose effective teaching strategies based on the selected objectives	46	43.4%	20	18.9%	40	37.7%
6. Not enough time to produce appropriate material for instruction.	24	22.6%	31	29.2%	51	48.1%
B. Barriers Related To Teaching Contents						
7. Lacking references which address the area's educational needs.	18	17%	20	18.9%	68	64.2%
8. Insufficient time to properly look for and arrange materials for instruction.	31	29.2%	32	30.2%	43	40.6%
9. Translation of medical words into local language is challenging.	34	32.1%	17	16%	55	51.9%
10. The problem of transforming a topic content or instructional content into simple terms	24	22.6%	27	25.5%	55	51.9%
11. The careful selection of health education materials.	19	17.9%	32	30.2%	55	51.9%
12. The large amount of material available causes to overload.	34	32.1%	19	17.9%	53	50%
C. Barriers Related To Audio-Visual Aids						
13. Unable to arrange suitable audiovisual aids	18	17%	24	22.6%	64	60.4%
14. Audio-Visual aids are not handled or used effectively enough.	27	25.5%	32	30.2%	47	44.3%
15. Unable to use modern technology or updated audiovisual aids.	31	29.2%	21	19.8%	54	50.9%
16. The expensive planning costs for the audio-visual content.	20	18.9%	10	9.4%	76	71.7%

Table 3 reveals barriers nursing students encounter during the preparation phase of health education: 56.6% of the participants admitted that they were unable to accurately identify clients' learning needs while 61.3% found it difficult to manage many clients. Almost half (45.3%) have a problem in categorizing the client's needs, and 40.6% struggle to define measurable objectives for health education. Lack of time in preparing affects the preparation of material as per the interest of students along with the fact that 48.1% of students fail to prepare materials on time. Moreover, 64.2% stated that they do not have any related educational material, and 51.9% reported difficulties in understanding medical terminology. About AV-aid, the largest percentage of 60.4% reported that they find it quite hard to source the right materials, while 71.7% assumed that it is expensive.

Table 4: Barriers in the Implementation Stage of Health Education

n=106

A. Barriers Related To Students:	Disagree		Neutral		Agree	
	N	%	n	%	n	%
1. Lacking health education skills and knowledge	24	22.6%	23	21.7%	59	55.7%
2. Unable to attract the client's attention to the problem.	24	22.6%	29	27.4%	53	50%
3. Unable of giving examples of the instructional objectives.	37	34.9%	26	24.5%	43	40.6%
4. Unable to provide the subject's writing and materials for instruction	24	22.6%	22	20.8%	60	56.6%
5. An obstacle in providing information in an organized format.	21	19.8%	23	21.7%	62	58.5%
6. Ineffective way to communicate	31	29.2%	21	19.8%	54	50.9%
7. Inadequate confidence in self.	33	31.1%	21	19.8%	52	49.1%
8. Inability to start conversations among the clients.	31	29.2%	18	17%	57	53.8%
9. Difficult to summarize the topic or emphasize the main points.	36	34%	27	25.5%	43	40.6%
10 Inadequate peer group collaboration and support	26	24.5%	30	28.3%	50	47.2%
B. Barriers Related To Clients						
11 A lack of readiness & motivation to learn of the clients.	14	13.2%	23	21.7%	69	65.1%
12 A lack of trust with students as information providers.	17	16%	25	23.6%	64	60.4%
13 Clients' limitations on time	36	34%	27	25.5%	43	40.6%
14 Clients are aware of this topic before.	40	37.7%	30	28.3%	36	34%
15 The cultural background of the clients affects the response to the knowledge	15	14.2%	20	18.9%	71	67%
16 Refusal of clients to listen to students	25	23.6%	24	22.6%	57	53.8%
17 Lack of feedback from clients and direct communication	27	25.5%	24	22.6%	55	51.9%
C. Barriers Related To Environment						
18 The uncomfortable location for health education.	18	17%	22	20.8%	66	62.3%
19 Disturbance and distraction.	23	21.7%	22	20.8%	61	57.5%
20 Environmental influences are difficult to handle.	18	17%	24	22.6%	64	60.4%
21 Not Enough privacy	29	27.4%	15	14.2%	62	58.5%

Table 4 outlines barriers to implementing health education: Clients' lack of motivation and preparedness was cited by 65.1% as a major barrier, while 55.7% of students believed they lacked sufficient skills and knowledge. 62.3% of respondents agreed that teaching was hindered by uncomfortable environments. Furthermore, 57.5% had difficulties with noise and interruptions during sessions, and 50.0% had problems retaining attention from clients.

Table 5: Barriers in the Terminal Stage of Health Education

n=106

A. Barriers Related Evaluation	Disagree		Neutral		Agree	
	n	%	n	%	N	%
1. Unable to receive feedback upon health education.	20	18.9%	20	18.9%	66	62.3%
2. Unable to formulate evaluation questions.	35	33%	17	16%	54	50.9%
3. Lack of familiarity with different methods of evaluation.	15	14.2%	29	27.4%	62	58.5%
4. Not enough time for evaluating the client's knowledge	40	37.7%	12	11.3%	54	50.9%

Table 5 highlights key barriers in health education at the terminal stage: 62% of the students stated that feedback on efforts was insufficient, approximately 51% of the students were not able to develop the evaluation questions and approximately 58.5% did not learn any methods of evaluation. Additionally, 50.9% responded that time constraint affected their ability to assess the clients based on their knowledge.

ANALYSIS:

Challenges of Health Education:

The current study revealed that 55.7 % agreed that they never possessed the correct health education skills and knowledge. This is consistent with the conclusion made by (Ravindra & Borude, 2023), where only 53.6% of students affirmed their readiness to face a group education environment. Furthermore, 65.1% of students that took part in the study, pointed out clients' unwillingness and their perceived motivation to learn a major challenges; the findings of which validate the studies (Mohammed et al., 2019) which 91.5% of the students indicated the same challenge. In addition, 62.3% of students stated that environmental discomfort including; unsuitable places for health education affected its delivery. This is in line with the difficulties found by (Ashipala & Matundu, 2023; Fallahnezhad et al., 2023) which stated that environmental factors were often mentioned as barriers.

Barriers to Health Education:

Barriers during the Preparation Phase: In this study, 44.6% of students said they do not have sufficient time for searching and preparing teaching content adequately. This is in line with the work of (Carless-Kane & Nowell, 2023), who found time as the main challenge exhibited by students. Similarly, 54% of participants had issues in translating medical terms into the local language; this is in line with what was reported in (Baumeister et al., 2021). Similarly, 63% of our participants had issues in simplifying complex terminology. Furthermore, 42.6% stated high costs experienced while preparing audio-visual materials which corresponds with (Ravindra & Borude, 2023) where 65.2 % of students responded the same.

Barriers during the Conducting Phase:

In the current study, it was established that 30% of the students experienced challenges on clients' inability and/ or unwillingness to learn. This is in agreement with other researchers whereby lack of motivation among the clients was identified as a main barrier (Kim & Kim, 2023). In addition, 51.6%

reported that noise and distraction interfered with carrying out health education, while 90.6% realized that these environmental factors were barriers (Guttman et al., 2021).

Barriers during the Termination Phase: In the current study, about half of the students (50.9%) responded that they did not have adequate time to evaluate clients' knowledge. A similar conclusion is made by Mohammed et al., where 67.5% of students agreed on similar time constraints that affected their evaluation process (Mohammed et al., 2019; Ravindra & Borude, 2023).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSION:

The study found significant barriers and challenges impact the effectiveness of BSN students. More than half of the students stated they lacked the skills and knowledge required for health education. Many acknowledged that environmental uneasiness from inappropriate teaching locations, as well as clients' lack of readiness and motivation, were major barriers. Barriers were evident during the preparation phase; where many students reported insufficient time adequately to prepare teaching content. Several participants expressed concerns about the high costs associated with creating audio-visual materials and faced challenges in translating medical terminology into the local language. During the conducting phase, challenges related to clients' lack of motivation and readiness was common, while noise and other interruptions diminished instructional effectiveness. In the termination phase, almost half of the students reported that they were unable to assess their clients' knowledge adequately in limited time. Concerning the provision of health education, it is essential to know these barriers and challenges. Solving these will enhance the nursing students' skills and preparedness, ultimately enhancing in client health education. Educational institutions can effectively assist nursing students to overcome these challenges and contribute to positive transformations in the delivery of public health education.

LIMITATIONS:

- The study relies on self-reported data from BSN students, which may be influenced by individual biases and perceptions.
- A non-probability purposive sampling method was used, limiting generalizability to other populations or settings.
- The study focused solely on one institution in Hyderabad, limiting the diversity of the sample.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Organize monthly seminars that address important aspects relating to communication techniques and technological integration into health promotion campaigns.
- Local health care organizations should be engaged so that students can obtain practical experience and help to overcome environmental barriers.

- Promote nursing students practical experiences in the delivery of health education principles under the supervision of qualified nurses.
- Offer specific curriculum-time blocks where students can assess their abilities to evaluate the client's knowledge and to provide feedback.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this study have declared no conflicts of interest.

FUNDING SOURCE

No funding is used to conduct this research.

REFERENCES

- Nie, Q., Liang, W., Xue, Y., Pan, L., Jiang, M., & He, F. (2024). Chronic hypertension diagnosed before or during pregnancy and its effects on pregnancy outcomes. *Journal of Human Hypertension*, 1-7.
- Aron, M. B., Ndambo, M. K., Munyaneza, F., Mulwafu, M., Makungwa, H., Nhlema, B., & Connolly, E. (2023). A time-motion study of community health workers delivering community-based primary health care in Neno District, Malawi. *Human Resources for Health*, 21(1), 51.
- Ashipala, D. O., & Matundu, M. (2023). Nursing students' experiences of communication in a multilingual and multicultural clinical environment: A qualitative study. *Nursing open*, 10(10), 6875-6884.
- Badulla, W. F., Alshakka, M., & Mohamed Ibrahim, M. I. (2023). Health Education, Promotion, and Prevention in LMICs. In *Encyclopedia of Evidence in Pharmaceutical Public Health and Health Services Research in Pharmacy* (pp. 796-816). Springer.
- Baumeister, A., Chakraverty, D., Aldin, A., Seven, Ü. S., Skoetz, N., Kalbe, E., & Woopen, C. (2021). "The system has to be health literate, too"-perspectives among healthcare professionals on health literacy in transcultural treatment settings. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21, 1-16.
- Benes, S., & Alperin, H. (2022). *The essentials of teaching health education: Curriculum, instruction, and assessment*. Human Kinetics.
- Betancurth-Loaiza, D. P., Pico-Merchán, M. E., & Castillo, L. O. (2024). Community practice in nursing programs in the context of primary health care. *Entramado*, 20(1), 1.
- Carless-Kane, S., & Nowell, L. (2023). Nursing students learning transfer from classroom to clinical practice: An integrative review. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 103731.
- DeMarco, R., & Healey-Walsh, J. (2023). *Community and public health nursing: evidence for practice*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Fallahnezhad, T., Aghaie, B., Norouzadeh, R., Ebadi, A., & Abbasinia, M. (2023). The challenges of nursing presence at the patient's bedside from the perspective of nurses: a qualitative study. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Sciences*, 33(2).
- Ferreira, R., Baixinho, C. L., Ferreira, Ó. R., Nunes, A. C., Mestre, T., & Sousa, L. (2022). Health promotion and disease prevention in the elderly: the perspective of nursing students. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 12(2), 306.

- Gonella, S., Viottini, E., Gastmans, C., Tambone, S., Conti, A., Campagna, S., & Dimonte, V. (2024). Lived experience of ethical challenges among undergraduate nursing students during their clinical learning. *Nursing Ethics*, 09697330241262311.
- Guttman, O. T., Lazzara, E. H., Keebler, J. R., Webster, K. L., Gisick, L. M., & Baker, A. L. (2021). Dissecting communication barriers in healthcare: a path to enhancing communication resiliency, reliability, and patient safety. In (Vol. 17, pp. e1465-e1471): LWW.
- Hamidzadeh, Y., Kamran, A., Shekarchi, A., & Moghaddam, H. R. (2020). Health Education Programs Challenges in Rural Communities: Experiences of Health Educators and Healthcare Authorities. *Annali di Igiene, Medicina Preventiva e di Comunità*, 32(6).
- Hwang, Y., & Oh, J. (2020). Factors affecting health-promoting behaviors among nursing students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(17), 6291.
- Iduye, D., Vukic, A., Waldron, I., Price, S., Sheffer, C., McKibbin, S.,...Yu, Z. (2021). Educators' strategies for engaging diverse students in undergraduate nursing education programs: A scoping review protocol. *JBIEvidence Synthesis*, 19(5), 1178-1185.
- Khamaiseh, A. M., & Altarawneh, F. Z. (2023). Factors and barriers influencing practice of health education among nursing students in Jordan. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 12(1), 441.
- Kim, S., & Kim, M. (2023). Nursing students' experiences and perceptions of barriers to the implementation of person-centred care in clinical settings: A qualitative study. *Nursing open*, 10(3), 1889-1899.
- Koelen, M. A., & Van den Ban, A. W. (2023). *Health education and health promotion*. BRILL.
- Komalasari, R. (2024). Empowering Informed Healthcare Choices in Rural Areas: SIKDA, a Novel Model for Enhancing Patient Access to Reliable Consumer Health Information. In *Emerging Engineering Technologies and Industrial Applications* (pp. 148-172). IGI Global.
- Mohammed, N. Y., Elkaluby, E. A., & Mohamed, A. M. (2019). Nursing students' perspectives regarding challenges and barriers of health education at different community clinical settings in Alexandria, Egypt. *Int J Novel Res Healthc Nurs*, 6, 488-502.
- Pueyo-Garrigues, M., Pardavila-Belio, M. I., Canga-Armayor, A., Esandi, N., Alfaro-Díaz, C., & Canga-Armayor, N. (2022). NURSES'knowledge, skills and personal attributes for providing competent health education practice, and its influencing factors: a cross-sectional study. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 58, 103277.

- Ravindra, P. S., & Borude, S. (2023). A study to identify the challenges and barriers while imparting health education in community among students from selected nursing institutes of Pune city. *Lat. Am. J. Pharm*, 42, 6.
- Reid, K., Armstrong, N., Todd, D., Ballard, L., Szczepaniak, C., & Tinsley, C. (2021). An examination of mental health, perceived barriers, and outreach recommendations among Rural college students. *American Journal of Health Education*, 52(2), 101-110.
- Rudd, R. E., Anderson, J. E., Oppenheimer, S., & Nath, C. (2023). Health literacy: an update of medical and public health literature. In *Review of Adult Learning and Literacy, Volume 7* (pp. 175-204). Routledge.
- Rudnicka, E., Napierała, P., Podfigurna, A., Męczekalski, B., Smolareczyk, R., & Grymowicz, M. (2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) approach to healthy ageing. *Maturitas*, 139, 6-11.
- Sharma, M. (2021). *Theoretical foundations of health education and health promotion*. Jones & Bartlett Learning.
- Stock, C. (2022). Grand challenges for public health education and promotion. In (Vol. 10, pp. 917685): Frontiers Media SA.
- Wang, J., Guo, J., Wang, Y., Yan, D., Liu, J., Zhang, Y., & Hu, X. (2020). Use of profession-role exchange in an interprofessional student team-based community health service-learning experience. *BMC Medical Education*, 20, 1-10.